

TalX Workshop 5: The role of resource in developing Place-Based Adaptation Partnerships

Date: November 18th, 2021

Introduction

A changing climate poses a wide range of impacts and risks for society in Britain and Ireland. To prepare for the impacts of climate change, effective and sustainable adaptation action is needed on a cross-sectoral and multi-level basis. This needs to be underpinned by an increase in the capacity of organisations and communities to deliver adaptation actions in different places across Britain and Ireland.

As part of the EPA-funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TaIX) project, an adaptation Capability and Maturity Model (CMM) is being created for the five jurisdictions of Britain and Ireland (Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England). This model will provide a mechanism to enable place-based adaptation through the provision of a structured change process, illustrating the development of adaptation capabilities for all stakeholders acting in a place.

To develop the CMM a series of co-creation workshops are being held online that invite experienced adaptation practitioners and policymakers from across the Britain and Ireland to provide their insights and experiences of 'on the ground' adaptation and the capabilities required to deliver it effectively. The first of these workshops (practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places) was held on March 29th and 30th and invited practitioners from across the jurisdictions to identify priority capability themes for inclusion in the CMM. The priority capability themes identified included:

- Leadership and Ownership (**Leadership**)
- Research, Knowledge and Expertise (**Evidence**)
- Community Education, Engagement, Involvement and Empowerment (**Community**)
- Collaboration, Cross-Sectoral Networks and Partnerships (**Partnerships**)
- Sustained and Secure Funding and Resource (**Resource**)

For each priority theme, a dedicated workshop was held to explore that theme in detail. This report presents the raw data collected at the resource workshop, which took place on November 18th, 2021.

Defining Resource

For the workshop, and within the scope of the TaIX project, **resource** is interpreted as the funding, finance, human resources, expertise, capacity, assets and technology needed in order to carry out long term place-based adaptation partnerships and actions. Subcomponents include:

- **Assets**
 - Data and technology e.g., climate risk data and/ or models, records of climate impacts, GIS technology.
 - Engagement resources e.g., online meeting platforms and facilitation tools. in person meeting and workshop venues.
 - Adaptation and resilience assets e.g., hazard warning systems, blue and green infrastructure and natural coastal protection.
- **Human resources**
 - Staff time to lead and coordinate partnership activities. Teams, boards, committees or individuals that contribute different types of expertise, skills, insights and leadership.

- Access to specific skills needed to progress adaptation, e.g. ability to influence, risk managers, engineers, GIS and data analysts, community engagement.
- **Funding and finance**
 - Different funding mechanisms – grant funding, partnership funding models, public, private and blended finance.
 - Skills and capacity to access funding e.g. Understand funding and finance options, build business case for action, manage funding /finance and fulfil stakeholder management and reporting requirements.

Workshop Findings

To support workshop activities and prior to the workshop, a [pre-recorded video](#) was circulated to all participants which provides an overview of the TaIX project. The workshop was delivered online over one morning. The workshop commenced with presentations of two case studies from practice, including:

- Matt Ellis, Climate Resilience Officer at Greater Manchester Combined Authority, spoke about the IGNITION project, which aims to develop innovative financing solutions for investment in Greater Manchester’s natural environment.
- Paul Watkiss, Director of Paul Watkiss Associates, provided insight on resource mobilization for place-based adaptation in the Glasgow City Region and internationally

Slides from the presentations were circulated to participants. Following this, three interactive sessions were held using [Miro](#). The results are presented here. To note, the content within this document summarises the input received at the workshop. Additional analysis and refinement of this content is currently being undertaken to develop the CMM.

Work Session 1 Resourcing Requirements and Activities for Effective Partnerships

During this session, participants responded to the question, “What are the resources required for effective adaptation partnerships?”. Table 1 presents the results under specified headings.

Table 1 Feedback from participants on types of resource required for effective place-based adaptation partnerships

Theme	Content suggested at workshop
Assets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate risk data, socio-economic data for different scenarios, • Peer support, knowledge and data • Building links with local volunteer groups wildlife/flood action etc • Good facilitation platforms and whiteboards - have been essential • Ability to run hybrid meetings (maybe how things are in the future) - assets for this • Science communication hub - evidence based information provided to all parties - get ahead of misinformation • National/Regional climate hazard datasets and receptor vulnerability /sensitivity datasets • Inventory of natural assets that support adaptation to ensure that they are protected and enhanced • Data platforms to drive efficiencies and track progress
Human Resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need a central point of contact in the organisation – coordinator. Avoid situation where adaptation is a bolt on to someone’s current role. • Multi-disciplinary teams with a dedicated leader • Resources to monitor adaptation actions and climate risks as part of an adaptation pathway approach • Leadership • High-level buy-in is extremely helpful to both secure additional resource but also to raise awareness of the need for place-based approach. • Capacity building on climate risks and adaptation measures across organisation • Shared purpose and vision critical from the outset • Not just GIS technology but trained staff
Funding & Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of business case to attract initial seed funding is crucial; • Very difficult to establish successful adaptation programme regionally without public sector investment as starter for 10 • Funding to develop projects and bring to stage of being 'investable' e.g., design and consents, consultation etc • Overarching potentially government or public backed umbrella fund which will remove risk • Although challenging, developing an outline vision for a climate ready region prior to engagement with potential stakeholders helps to sell the concept and requirement for investment • Frameworks or standards and intention from policy and legislation which identifies a phasing out of climate risk exposure over time will drive better private sector resilient investments • Assumption of a blended finance model from the outset with a full understanding of all of the potential elements • Ways to bridge the mismatch between public and societal benefits resulting from adaptation projects but the costs of implementation sitting with individuals e.g., private landowners • Legal advice for any contracting stage • Dedicating resources to resource mobilisation itself - so bringing in grants, and funding for developing resources and resource mobilisation planning • Working in a blended finance environment - currently people tend to operate in silos for funding • Challenging to get across the funding sources available and understand which ones are accessible to developed nations, also huge transaction cost in every LA applying to do similar projects across the country, we need a system that simplifies access and reduces transaction cost eg Blueprint projects that can be tweaked at the local level • Core funding for coordination
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buy-in across the partnership (preferably at all levels) • Strategy and policy needs to support action (especially project development and finance raising etc) • Public assets/funding/activity may need to be involved (Green infra maintenance burden for instance) engage widely and early • Recognition that it's not just about specific projects and outcomes - should be some flexibility to react and seize opportunities. • Leadership - you need to be supported in making the investment in adaptation action • Common language that uses mainstream terminology and does not exclude. • Cases & clear guidance on potential asset classes • Acceptance by funders that adaptation actions and planning is a dynamic process - space needed to fail.

Work Session 2 Unpacking finance for place-based adaptation partnerships

During this session, participants provided input into a table to explore finance of place-based projects. Results from the three breakout group discussions are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2 Feedback from participants exploring a place-based finance use case

Instruments	Actors	Project Cycle / Partnership Development Process		
		Conceptualisation	Appraisal	Implementation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grants: Green Infrastructure related Grants, guarantees, concessional loans, community ISAs, Community Municipal Bonds, Section 106 Agreements Community Infrastructure levy - through planning National and European Funding Programmes Regeneration / new public sector builds municipal bonds Philanthropic Sources PPAs Government Tenders Philanthropic donations Site donations Business improvement district funding Corporate donations (ESG) Local discretionary funding pots Institutional Funding / Donor Funding / Industry (direct or indirectly related to Climate - e.g. Corporate and Social Responsibility (CSR) funding - issues with perceived Blended finance, equity, guarantees LA bonds PPPs Research linked funding e.g., PCAN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and Higher education bodies, public bodies, ESRC Volunteers Shareholders Donors Banks Trusts and Foundations Grant Makers Investors Public Sector Investors - institutional, personal investors, government, international climate funds, banks, financial regulators, financial services organisations Local Authority CPP People or institutions of high net worth Civic Society eNGOs local businesses British Business bank and Community wealth building and Credit Unions Public finance institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a clear case for support which can then be used across multiple funding sources Governance structure of lead organisation is key - need a separate governance arrangement that allows you to move funding around There are huge transaction costs involved in preparing a project for funding. e.g. project preparation, feasibility studies - huge investment - not efficient. Need to minimize - find ways of reducing transaction costs. Project preparation needs to happen at a regional level Business case development is essential - ideally in collaboration with sympathetic partners Requires lead body to catalyse and facilitate partnership working Early vision-setting key for buy-in - Need a shared vision and to meet objectives of various partners Get your 'buyers' involved early Understand the requirements of all partners Co-design Concept note - with identification of possible revenue streams Given the short-term nature of research funding - consideration of legacy needs to be a key part of how projects are set up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation is political issue in number of ways, so need buy-in from administration. Business case - back-and-forth between core organisation / partners to ensure robustness before seeking final funding A question is how well we can move from a project approach to a more embedded and BAU approach Business Case - 5 case model if public monies involved, you would need a treasury (or similar) business case - so start early Who will sign it off (across the partners) and what are their processes/timelines? Focus on appraisal and bring partners together will pay dividends to ensure project design speaks to all partners - to ensure all partner outcomes achieved Business case based on the needs of the partners and tailored to suit Agreed Indicators / metrics of progress / success 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous review and improvement MEL

Work Session 3

During this session, participants mapped out the evolution of place-based adaptation partnerships from those just starting out (less developed or mature) through to well-established and effective partnerships (more developed and mature). Findings presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Feedback from workshop participants in how resourcing requirements and activities develop over time and as a partnership grows. Content gathered related to characteristics and specific activities required in relation to resourcing place based adaptation

	Stage One	Stage Two	Stage Three
Description (Characteristics)	Resources are beginning to be identified and gathered, in an ad-hoc fashion. The potential resource needs for the partnership are not yet fully identified. Resource requirements being developed in line with the outline vision for the partnership. Uncertain funding or only short-term funding is currently in place. Potential funding and finance is being scoped and possible revenue streams highlighted. Assets are also being mapped in terms of what all members own or have to access to. Due to skill gaps, activities such as legal advice and finance skills are outsourced /external experts relied upon. Skills and knowledge being developed by learning from people, partnerships and places which are already mature and well-resourced. A governance model is being established, which helps to identify gaps in knowledge and where additional resource needs to be found.	Actual coordination and resource capacity is coming onstream, with clear knowledge / specifications about what investment amount is needed. A business case to attract initial seed funding has been completed and the partnership is undertaking technical studies and evaluation of options. Data and evidence collated by partnership is made available and accessible to all parties. Skills within partnership developed and strengthened including technical expertise, facilitation experience and finance insight. Options are being applied to across public and private finance sources. Methods to bridge the mismatch between public and societal benefits resulting from adaptation projects considered.	Long-term sufficient and sustainable resourcing secured for partnership. A pipeline of projects aligned against finances and enough coordinating / technical and legal resource to take to delivery is in place. A strong brand, well developed partnership with good reputation supports resourcing (through enhanced confidence from investors). The partnership is now recognised as main point of contact and conduit for adaptation in the area. There is an in-depth understanding of what various funders and investors require, and applications are successful. Investment has been de-risked from earlier learning and interventions. The partnership is seen as a focal point for expertise with wide ranging and well-regarded skills, expertise and insight including due diligence, fiduciary risk assessment and legal oversight. There is knowledge and capacity in place to translate research into useful practice. Blended finance is secured from multiple sources. Partnership is demonstrating bankability of adaptation projects.
Tasks (Activities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recruiting staff / identifying personnel or local champions Participate in city to city networks - sharing and lesson learning Governance structure of lead organisation is key - need a separate governance arrangement that allows you to move funding around e.g. house building is a good example. e.g. for HES problematic / not able to accept private funding beyond a certain threshold so different governance mechanism needed Secure initial funding to support further activities. There are huge transaction costs involved in preparing a project for funding. e.g. project preparation, feasibility studies - huge investment - not efficient. Need to minimize - find ways of reducing transaction costs. Project Preparation activities. Investors are looking for bankable projects - need to get better at organisations working together to develop large scale funding propositions Project preparation needs to happen at a regional level - at the moment certain councils are benefiting disproportionately because they have developed the skills needed to win funding bids. Early engagement with stakeholders to identify regulatory / technical issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantify investment cost required for adaptation and net zero Large scale pilots of projects – where multiple stacked or private finance is starting to be brought in Develop a clear case for support which can then be used across multiple funding sources Business Case - 5 case model – being developed Focus on appraisal and bring partners together will pay dividends to ensure project design speaks to all partners - to ensure all partner outcomes achieved Explore how pensions could be used to invest locally in local place-based investments – Grantham Institute researching this Dedicated funding for partnership coordinator or project management is a given with transparency on funding Agreed Indicators / metrics of progress / success Glue people - the linking people who convene, facilitate and can switch between the bigger picture and the detail are employed/funded by partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having de-risked investment pipeline and use grant finance to de-risk rather than bank rolling Be able to aggregate actions to create pipeline - at regional level Securing 10–15-year finance, get that on capital market on low returns, mixing and blending financial instruments - perhaps use guarantee for further risk and development Look at revenue not just finance models - debt instruments Having a strong brand - helps develop bond model and provides credibility to investors Ensure robust governance arrangements in place to manage long term resourcing Respond to consultations – e.g., when funders go out to consultation on (grants) programme ensure adaptation included Be aware of Disclosures driving private sector and take advantage of opportunities that may emerge Dedicated staff responsible for income and servicing partnership approach –

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need a shared vision and to meet objectives of various partners • Early gap analysis helps to identify who else needs to be involved • Narrow focus - identify funding gap - funders may have geographic specific interest and different outcome requirements - need to track. • Research and data - technical studies and evaluation • Ensure appropriate resources for communications activities - from partnership inception right through is hugely important e.g., website townhall meetings newsletters etc • Dedicated funding for partnership coordinator or project management is a given with transparency on funding • Develop initial Concept note - aligned to type of organisations/activities involved in partnership - with identification of possible revenue streams • Identification of instrument, actor, and revenues/benefit streams • Given the short-term nature of research funding - consideration of legacy needs to be a key part of how projects are set up • A robust governance model is essential - helps to identify gaps in knowledge and where additional resource needs to be found • Although challenging, developing an outline vision for a climate ready region prior to engagement with potential stakeholders helps to sell the concept and requirement for investment • Common language that uses mainstream terminology and does not exclude. 		
Case Studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manhood Peninsula Partnership • Belfast Living water programme • Maharees conservation in Kerry and coastal Community liaison group in Fingal county council for Portrane area (interreg CCAT project involved here too) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IGNITION Manchester • Climate Ready Clyde 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hong Kong case study

Conclusions

The workshop helped draw out insights and information on resources required for place-based adaptation partnerships. It highlighted the experiences of the adaptation practitioners, researchers and community members across Britain and Ireland. The input received at the workshop is now being reviewed and combined with findings from the academic and grey literature to inform the development of the Capability-Maturity Model.

The TalX team would like to thank all the attendees for their active participation and willingness to share their insights and experience in order to promote and enable climate adaptation actions in Britain and Ireland. We would also like to thank our speakers Matt Ellis and Paul Watkiss for making the time to present detailed and inspiring case studies.

Appendix 1: Participant list for the Resource workshop

Country	Name
Scotland	Keith Masson
Scotland	Zoe Clelland
Scotland	Heather MacNaughton
Scotland	Paul Watkiss
Ireland	David Dodd
Ireland	Cathal O'Mahony
Ireland	Jeremy Gault
Wales	Fen Turner
Northern Ireland	Stephen Jones
Northern Ireland	Jimmy Convery
Northern Ireland	Cathy Burns
Northern Ireland	Debbie Caldwell
England	Matt Ellis
England	Kristen Guida
England	Kate Lonsdale
England	Carolyn Cobbold
England	Clare foster

Appendix 2: Workshop Agenda

Agenda for the TalX Resource Workshop 10:00-12:30 18th November 2021

Background

As part of the Irish EPA funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TalX - www.Talx.ie) project we are developing a Capability Maturity Model (CMM) to help progress place-based climate adaptation across the UK and Ireland. The CMM aims to support adaptation practitioners across the UK and Ireland in progressing planning and implementation of effective place-based adaptation partnerships.

Following on from an initial workshop exploring practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places (which took place March 2021), 5 priority capabilities were identified. A series of workshops exploring these capabilities in detail is now taking place. The upcoming workshop on November 18th focuses on the topic of 'resource'.

Useful Information:

- In advance of the workshop and to make the most efficient use of time available, participants are asked to view a video presentation providing an overview of the TalX project [here](#).
- To support workshop activities, MIRO platforms will be used. You can find a short introductory video on how to use Miro [here](#).
- The meeting will take place via MS Teams (the meeting link can be found in the meeting invitation)

Agenda:

Time	Title	Topic
10:00	Welcome	Overview of the aims and agenda of the workshop
10:10	Learning from Practice	Presentations from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matt Ellis, Climate Resilience Officer at Greater Manchester Combined Authority, will be speaking about the IGNITION project, which aims to develop innovative financing solutions for investment in Greater Manchester's natural environment • Paul Watkiss, Director of Paul Watkiss Associates, will provide insight on resource mobilization for place-based adaptation in the Glasgow City Region and internationally
10:40	Work session # 1 – Defining resource requirements of effective partnerships	Identification of the resources and associated resourcing activities required for effective adaptation partnerships
10:55	Work session #2: Deep dive into finance	Exercise to identify the mechanisms, stakeholders and activities associated with financing place-based adaptation partnerships.
11:35	BREAK	
11:40	Work session #3: Mapping the evolution of resourcing place-based adaptation partnerships	Group discussion on resourcing needs and activities as partnership develops and matures.
12:20	Wrap Up and Close	Summary of the workshop findings and next steps

